

UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK

What are the outer limits of what is legitimate in the tax avoidance activities of multinational groups of companies? A different multifaceted approach to tax avoidance from the opposite point of view to what is fashionable.

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Declaration

I, the author of this dissertation, declare that no matter which I have used before, or have had published, has been used in this dissertation. The Figures and Tables in Appendixes A, B and C are reproduced and contain data from: Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264; Daniel Bunn, 'Decades in Corporate Taxation: Trends in Corporate Revenues and Rate' (*Tax Foundation*, 8 July 2020); Deloitte, 'Corporate-Tax Rates 2020' (Deloitte, 2020); PWC, 'Luxembourg: Corporate Income determination' (PWC, 2 July 2020); PWC, 'Luxembourg: Taxes on Corporate Income' (PWC, 2 July 2020); UNCTAD based on Fuest et al. (2013b); United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, *World Investment Report 2015: Reforming International Investment Governance*, (World Investment Report, 2015); Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9.

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Abstract

The tax planning of multinational group of companies is constantly gaining more ground in debates concerning the tax avoidance activities and their relation, if any, to tax evasion practices. Unsurprisingly, the legitimacy of the concept of tax avoidance in MNGs has come under constant criticism, and severe scrutiny. As a consequence, a growing momentum against MNGs' tax avoidance activities reform the public's perception concerning MNGs and their tax planning. This dissertation will contribute to the already existing literature, research and policy papers by considering the positive elements and the advantages concerning the tax practices of MNGs in relation to the public's prosperity. It clarifies, that tax avoidance is entirely different for tax evasion and has to be treated as a lawful sophisticated tax planning in alignment with the law. This dissertation, through the political philosophy underpinning and the ethics of taxation, underlines that any government's intervention in the private sphere of taxpayers should not take place arbitrarily and inexhaustibly for the common good. Governments should take into consideration the benefits of the private sector and should not interfere with its operations. Bloated welfare countries intervening to the business operations of MNGs are distorting the national economy resulting in the emergence of dangers in the commercial, economic and social balances. The dissertation offers a series of persuasive arguments in favour of the multinational groups of companies' tax avoidance activities and paves the way for fiscal and political reshuffles which have to take place at the international tax environment. Through the dissertation, it is argued that The MNGs should not be threatened with sanctions and social condemnations. At any rate, according to the dissertation, the tax avoidance activities as implemented by the MNGs have to be observed and be treated as lawful methods of tax planning which coexist with the current national and international tax regimes.

This paper will leave the reader with a good impression in regard to tax avoidance activities and will lead him to critical thinking towards the literature and debates which observe and address tax avoidance schemes as a tax practice completely unlawful, immoral and economically unfair

Chapter 1

Introduction

The need for research, examination and clarification of multinational groups of companies (MNGs) tax planning is continually gaining more ground on the occasion of the long-lasting, but misguided, trend to confuse and treat tax avoidance similarly with tax evasion. At a time when the legitimacy of the concept of tax avoidance in MNGs has come under constant criticism, and severe scrutiny, a growing momentum against MNGs' tax avoidance activities reforms the public's perception concerning MNGs and their tax planning.

These points result in questions and debates concerning the ethics, the political and fiscal aspect of MNGs' tax strategies. This dissertation will contribute to the already existing literature, research and policy papers by considering the second, neglected, side of the same coin concerning the tax practices of MNGs. The overall aim is to present data and arguments which highlight in a "revolutionary", non-fashionable way the positive shade of the MNGs' tax planning activities which contribute efficiently to the public's prosperity. Once a for all, it needs to be clarified that the tax avoidance by MNGs, as opposed to tax evasion, has to be treated as lawful sophisticated tax planning methods in alignment with the law.

With this thought, the dissertation is divided into seven parts beyond this introduction to critically analyse the outer limits of what is legitimate in the tax avoidance activities of multinational groups of companies.

To begin with, Chapter 2 offers the philosophical background on which the following discussions will be properly supported since the legal system and any legal debate cannot be evaluated in isolation and separately from their political, philosophical and social origins. Chapter 3 examines the functional roles and the evolution of corporate tax which will pave the way for a more targeted discussion about the disadvantages posed by globalisation and the consolidation of the digital economy. Thereinafter, Chapter 4 introduces possible factors which motivate the sophisticated tax planning by MNGs and offers an insight into the tax avoidance schemes as implemented by MNGs, which constitute an art form of tax planning. The tide of public opinion against the MNGs' tax planning and the ever-increasing, ongoing, criticism against MNGs will be examined in Chapter 5. Then, Chapter 6 will offer comprehensive definitions for the tax practices of tax avoidance and tax evasion and will create a fertile ground for the introduction of persuasive arguments in favour of the MNGs' tax avoidance activities. Last but not least, concluding remarks appear in Chapter 7, which will emphasise the importance of the current dissertation and will stress the research outcomes.

Chapter 2

Political Philosophy and The Ethics of Taxation.

Tax theory and tax policy are multidimensional, intricate and specialised subjects, mainly, surrounded by a purely economic cloak. However, taxation, due to its close and vital link with the state's and citizens interaction, should hold a notable position at the core of political philosophy.¹ These statements are confirmed by the fact that governments continue to expand their economic influence and control in social and commercial aspects of everyday life over the years.² Therefore, the current chapter could not start otherwise than to lay a philosophical underpinning which will both add significant value in the rest of the content and will pave the way for the achievement of conceptual clarity and adequate coverage of all the topic's aspects, under examination, in this dissertation.

To address questions regarding tax and its political, economic and social ramifications, arguments will be presented and deployed by prominent philosophers and economist who took an active part in debates concerning taxation, its amount, its legitimate objectives, the taxpayers' consent and their interactions with the tax policies, as well as the governments' interference in property, privacy and social justice.³

2.1 The Ethical Theories' Perspective

To begin with, the perspectives of the main ethical theories will be examined.

¹Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; V.S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, *AmJSocial* 758,764 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents> last accessed 9 August 2020; Martin O'Neil and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives*, (first published 2018, OUP 2018) ch12 <<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780199609222.001.0001/oso-9780199609222-chapter-13>> last accessed 9 August 2020; Martin O'Neil and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives*, (first published 2018, OUP 2018) ch1 <<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780199609222.001.0001/oso-9780199609222-chapter-2>> last accessed 9 August 2020, and; Martin O'Neil and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives*, (first published 2018, OUP 2018) 1,17 <<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780199609222.001.0001/oso-9780199609222-chapter-1>> last accessed 9 August 2020; see Introduction.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid, footnote 1.

2.1.1 Utilitarianism

Firstly, according to the normative ethical theory of utilitarianism,⁴ as founded by Jeremy Bentham,⁵ the main economic aim is the overall happiness and satisfaction of the population, regardless of the stringiness of the wealth distribution. According to utilitarianism, taxes together with the imposing governments levying them and their sovereignty over taxpayers are a requisite “marriage” in achieving resources’ redistribution, to society, for the population’s maximum satisfaction.⁶ Nevertheless, the theory succumbs to a contradiction since high rates of tax prevent and reduce and investment initiatives resulting in no sufficient resources for redistribution.⁷ Besides, a high ration of redistribution encompasses the danger of minimal or zero resources’ share for general enjoyment.

In terms of the taxation’s legitimate purposes, Utilitarians applaud the promotion of law, order and public services since they would satisfy, severally and jointly, more desires in the social whole, by promoting, even prima facie, general economic equality between the taxpayers.⁸

Last but not least, utilitarianism as a normative ethical theory, and an advocate of the aggregate welfare, will not be, expressively, against some taxpayers’ behaviours, such as tax avoidance, for the following two, most apparent, reasons. First, since utilitarianism is based on economic efficiency and, several times, the use of taxes is economically inefficient (i.e. social engineering), the tax avoidance’s application is justified.⁹ Second, because it is suggested that tax avoidance activities do not vanish wealth; in contrast, wealth remains to the private sector’s fund instead of being disbursed to the public sector. Lastly, the only concern regarding the tax avoidance practices would be the possible danger of reducing the population’s overall happiness because of the feasible tax burden shifting from the rich onto the modest and poor citizens.¹⁰

⁴Welch C, ‘Utilitarianism’ in John Eatwell, Murray Milgate, Peter Newman (eds), *The Invisible Hand*, (Palgrave Macmillan 1989) <https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-349-20313-0_35#citeas> last accessed 9 August 2020, and; Richard Baron, ‘The Ethics of Taxation’(Philosophy Now, Issue 90, 2012)<https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

⁵Brian Duignan and John P. Plamenatz, ‘Jeremy Bentham, British philosopher and economist’ (*Encyclopedia Britannica*, 1998) <<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Jeremy-Bentham>> last accessed 9 August 2020.

⁶Richard Baron, ‘The Ethics of Taxation’(Philosophy Now, Issue 90, 2012)<https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

⁷Richard Baron, ‘The Ethics of Taxation’(Philosophy Now, Issue 90, 2012)<https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

⁸No ethicists would support unlimited application of any good things through the tax system; Ibid, footnote 7.

⁹Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch10 <https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9_10#citeas> last accessed 9 August 2020.

¹⁰Richard Baron, ‘The Ethics of Taxation’(Philosophy Now, Issue 90, 2012)<https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

2.1.2 Deontology

Deontology defines and delimits ethics based on the idea of duty.¹¹ The 18th-century German instigator of critical philosophy,¹² Immanuel Kant was the first to designate deontological theories whose foundations lie in the conformity of an action or omission to some absolute duties.¹³

One commonly known duty in deontology is the duty in respecting other peoples' property rights.¹⁴ However, such duty in respecting other peoples' property rights has a twofold interpretive result and value in terms of taxation.¹⁵ Firstly, it could be implied that taxation is unjust and therefore should not exist since tax imposition intervenes compulsorily in property rights. Secondly, with a different, but permissible, interpretation of the duty and according to property rights respect, tax imposition is justified as a means of compensation for the use of any social resources and benefits. Nevertheless, we should bear in mind that is not a "bulletproof" and realistic argument to urge people to give up public resources they do not need in order not to pay the relevant tax.¹⁶ In addition to the practical difficulties of checking and identifying the individual use of public benefits in large societies, it is likely to create economic and social unrest.

Furthermore, most of the taxation' objectives are in alignment with deontology;¹⁷ mainly purposes of aiding the poor or modernising public services. According to deontologists, in order to check and justify whether something, the objectives of taxation, in that case, is legitimate or not, they apply Kant's categorical imperative.¹⁸ Depending on this induction's

¹¹ Alexander, Larry and Michael Moore, 'Deontological Ethics', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter edn, 2016) <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2016/entries/ethics-deontological/> last accessed 22 August 2020; Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

¹² Johnson, Robert and Adam Cureton, 'Kant's Moral Philosophy', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring edn, 2019) <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2019/entries/kant-moral/> last accessed 20 August 2020; Herman Jean de Vleeschauwer, 'Kantianism' (*Encyclopædia Britannica*, 10 March 2016) <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Kantianism>> last accessed 20 August 2020.

¹³ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; Johnson, Robert and Adam Cureton, 'Kant's Moral Philosophy', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring edn, 2019) <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2019/entries/kant-moral/> last accessed 20 August 2020; Herman Jean de Vleeschauwer, 'Kantianism' (*Encyclopædia Britannica*, 10 March 2016) <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Kantianism>> last accessed 20 August 2020.

¹⁴ Alexander, Larry and Michael Moore, 'Deontological Ethics', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter edn, 2016) <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2016/entries/ethics-deontological/> last accessed 22 August 2020; Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

¹⁵ Deontology ethics does what it always does. It creates polarization and makes us uncertain about what to presume.

¹⁶ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

¹⁷ Ibid, footnote 8.

¹⁸ Johnson, Robert and Adam Cureton, 'Kant's Moral Philosophy', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring edn, 2019) <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2019/entries/kant-moral/> last accessed 20 August 2020;

results, they, philosophically, surround the findings under the duty argument.¹⁹ However, it is remarkable to note that despite Kant's absolute belief in the duty of aiding the poor, he never had in mind, or at least he never expressed explicitly, a tax-funded and orientated welfare state for the fulfilment of these duties.²⁰

Lastly, concerning the taxpayers' conduct and investigating whether, and to what extent, tax avoidance is ethic and justified, deontologist both support and insist on the duty to obey the law. Nevertheless, someone who engages in tax avoidance practices could easily argue that in order to apply these sophisticated methods of tax avoidance, he does nothing else but obey the law in a specialised way.²¹ That argument undoubtedly creates a fertile ground both for the discussion's coherent continuation and purposes in this dissertation.

2.1.3 Virtue Ethics

Virtue ethics is the third dominant approach to ethics and emphasises the virtues or moral character one should own. Moreover, virtue ethics, in the current discussion, have a broad connotation of virtues.²² The virtue ethics' founders are the ancient Greek philosophers Aristotle and Plato. Even now many of the theory's principles can be traced around the philosophical world.²³

Virtue ethicists, in terms of taxation' justice, consider that with moderate or low tax rates more virtues are likely to be required and exercised since the offered financial incentives encourage people to both meet and apply their talents.²⁴ Therefore, instead of a high rate tax burden, a moderate tax rate is likely to bring people close with the virtue of independence and complacent. As a result, they will not be depended either on subsidies or assistance from the government. Furthermore, citizens with high earnings and take-home pay will be able to afford

Herman Jean de Vleeschauwer, 'Kantianism' (*Encyclopædia Britannica*, 10 March 2016) <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Kantianism>> last accessed 20 August 2020; Immanuel Kant, 'Introduction' in Mary J. Gregor (ed), *The Metaphysics of Morals* (CUP 2013) <<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511809644>> last accessed 21 August 2020; Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020.

¹⁹Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

²⁰ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid, footnote 20.

²³ Hursthouse Rosalind, Pettigrove Glen 'Virtue Ethics', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring edn, 2017) <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2017/entries/ethics-virtue/>> last accessed 20 August 2020;

²⁴ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020.

charitable donations as well as to engage more actively either in charity work or civic and judicial services for the overall welfare.²⁵

Regarding the taxation's purposes, virtue ethicists promote the empowerment of the state's provisions and public services, and they underline that through distribution and social solidarity, the people's virtues and talents will flourish.²⁶ Nonetheless, as we mentioned, in virtue ethics theory, voluntary charity is widely accepted as a greater virtue than tax coercive payments for achieving such purposes.

Lastly, virtue ethicists view tax avoidance with disfavour. According to them, those who exploit rules and other relevant loopholes to avoid tax, and simultaneously are aware that these practices are likely to cause an unintended distribution of the tax burden, are far away from exercising virtues. However, given the preceding, a logical question arises. In a case in which a disproportionate tax burden has fallen on a virtuous taxpayer due to someone's else immorality, laziness or inability to exercise virtues; what would be the response of virtue ethicists if the taxpayer participated in tax avoidance practices for that additional figure that is not generally due to him? Would such a taxpayer's behaviour, under these circumstances, would be in alignment with virtue ethics?

2.2 The Perspective of Political Philosophy

Taxation, due to its vital connection with the state's and citizens interaction, holds a notable position at the core of political philosophy.²⁷ After presenting the ethical theories' perspective in taxation, now, as we have mentioned in the preface of this chapter, we will present and employ arguments by prominent philosophers and economists. They took an active part in the political philosophy discussion concerning taxation and its social, political and economic branches.

In Robert Nozick's *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* and, John Rawls's *A Theory of Justice* have presented two diametrically opposite approaches to tax, the legitimacy of a tax system,

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid, footnote 8.

²⁷ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; V.S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, *AmJSocial* 758,764 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents> last accessed 9 August 2020; Martin O'Neil and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives*, (first published 2018, OUP 2018) ch12 <<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780199609222.001.0001/oso-9780199609222-chapter-13>> last accessed 9 August 2020; Martin O'Neil and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives*, (first published 2018, OUP 2018) ch1 <<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780199609222.001.0001/oso-9780199609222-chapter-2>> last accessed 9 August 2020, and; Martin O'Neil and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives*, (first published 2018, OUP 2018) 1,17 <<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780199609222.001.0001/oso-9780199609222-chapter-1>> last accessed 9 August 2020.

property rights and justice.²⁸ These contrasting philosophical poles brought by the libertarian (Nozick) and Rawlsian (J. Rawls) approaches to tax have deep roots in their similarly philosophical differentiation regarding property rights' nature.²⁹

To start with, R. Nozick in *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (1974) expressed that "Taxation of earning from labor is on a par with forced labor".³⁰ According to Nozick, taxation is a form of theft and violates self-ownership.³¹ Any peremptory fiscal contribution and financial distribution should only exist for the support of a minimal state;³² a state which promotes both security and property rights' enforcement as well as provides a sufficient legal framework for business and investment initiatives. Simultaneously, Nozick declares that any act of assistance and solidarity to benefit those in disadvantage should be completed by voluntary benevolence than by coercive engagement and payment.³³ Thus, any other coercive interference by taxation violates people's rights.³⁴

Last but not least, we find the origin of the above Nozick's approach in his philosophical view regarding property and property rights. For Nozick property and property rights are proportional and a result of both initial agreements and exchange processes which took place a long time ago. If these processes were legitimate at the past time, then the current property distribution and possession is just and justified. Therefore, there should be constraints in governments' interference to people's pre-existing/pre-political rights (i.e. property rights).

In contrast, according to Rawls, property rights are not pre-political restrictions on the government's political and economic interference. Instead, they are part of the "basic structure" of the so-called society which coexists together with other public rules as a contrivance of cooperation and harmonisation in favour of the whole society.³⁵ Through Rawls's *A Theory of Justice*, we understand that tax rules are only a part of many public rules which operate together as a complete system of rules and institutions.³⁶

Moreover, Rawls suggests that social benefits should be more accessible to people with the fewest advantages, thus eliminating social inequalities. Nevertheless, he expresses that a

²⁸ Robert Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (New York: Basic Books 1974); John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (HUP 1999) <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctvkjb25m>> last accessed 23 August 2020.

²⁹ Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018).

³⁰ Robert Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (New York: Basic Books 1974) 169-172

³¹ Robert Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (New York: Basic Books 1974) 169-172; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch12.

³² Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch12.

³³ Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction.

³⁴ Robert Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (New York: Basic Books 1974) 169-172; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch12.

³⁵ John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (HUP 1999) <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctvkjb25m>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch12.

³⁶ Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch12.

social and economic unequal system can be justified if the people facing inequalities have not tried to develop, or even apply, their talents in practice. Simultaneously, those in disadvantage, by observing the economic and social prosperity of the hard-working and entrepreneurial persons they will both recognise and be encouraged to explore the given incentives for creating a more prosperous future for themselves and their fellow citizens.³⁷

Therefore, we understand that, to some extent, Rawls prefers an unequal system with social and economic incentives over an economically egalitarian one³⁸. In light of the above, the Marxist Gerald Cohen accused Rawls that, philosophically, was too receptive of inequalities.³⁹

Many liberal philosophers support that the liberal egalitarian approach to tax policy not only avoids two challenges faced by a welfarist – consequentialist approach⁴⁰, namely the exploitation of the hard-working and the exploitation of the talented, but is also competent of recognising the distinction between fair and unfair inequalities.⁴¹ However, the main drawback for the liberal egalitarian approach to tax policy is that it required information and evidence that is not available to tax authorities; still, it can be used for tax policies' evaluation.⁴²

On the same side with Rawls, the Philosophers Liam Murphy and Thomas Nagel, through their book, *The Myth of Ownership: Taxes and Justice*,⁴³ posed an interesting challenge to Nozick's line regarding the existence of pre-political rights and the constraints on a government's intervention to property.⁴⁴ They developed on a broader sense the Rawlsian theory regarding taxes, and tax policy and they underlined that the idea of a pre-political/pre-existing right is without normative foundation.⁴⁵ According to L. Murphy and T. Nagel, a tax-levying state provides stability and security which allows and promotes high earnings. Thus, *The Myth of Ownership: Taxes and Justice* underlines that the importance of a maximum state

³⁷ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; V.S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, *AmJSocial* 758,764 https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents last accessed 9 August 2020

³⁸ Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 6.

³⁹ G A Cohen, *Rescuing Justice and Equality* (1st edn, HUP 2008); Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 10 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Studies have shown that there is no economic ground for graduated income tax: F.A. Hayek, *The Case Against Progressive Income Tax* (The Freeman 1953) 229-232; Walter Blum and Harry Kalven, *The Uneasy Case for Progressive Taxation* (UCP 1953); Karl Marx and Frederick Engels, *The Communist Manifesto* (first published 1848, International Publishers Co 2014).

⁴⁰ The welfarist – consequentialist approach was founded by James Mirrlees and defended by Liam Murphy and Tomas Nagel; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 6.

⁴¹ Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 6.

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ Liam Murphy and Thomas Nagel, *The Myth of Ownership: Taxes and Justice* (OUP 2002).

⁴⁴ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; Liam Murphy and Thomas Nagel, *The Myth of Ownership: Taxes and Justice* (OUP 2002).

⁴⁵ Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction.

should not be undermined since the wealth would be lower without the government's interference with distributions.⁴⁶

Furthermore, it is worthy of dedicating some space to John Locke's theory on taxation, property, and the private realm.⁴⁷ John Locke articulated in the *Second Treatise of Government* his philosophical ideas about taxation and a liberal government's place in society.⁴⁸

The quintessence of Locke's taxation theory, which is deontological with the following proviso, is found in the *Second Treatise of Government* (TTG2), and particularly in paragraphs 138-158.⁴⁹ Locke in paragraph 140, TTG2 offers a critical passage which predisposes us for his beneficial principle on the justice in taxation.⁵⁰ According to the Lockean theory everyone who enjoys his share of protection (from the government), should pay his proposition for its maintenance; still, the payment for the government's support must be accompanied with the payer's, who enjoys protection, consent.⁵¹

However, two questions arise after reading these lines, in paragraph 140, carefully. Does the concept of a protection's share imply that an advantaged and wealthy citizen should be enjoying more protection than the others? Or, the fact that someone possesses much land and chattels, thus having a broad, proportional, share of protection, signals his obligation to pay more taxes than the rest? Undoubtedly, Locke's taxation theory has been the subject of several debates as to its exact interpretation.⁵²

Thereinafter, in light of the preceding, to clarify Locke's taxation theory, we will explore Locke's philosophical tropes about property, consent and privacy. He developed his famous property theory in his two *Treatises of Government* in which he, notably, connected property with privacy and underlined the private's sphere distinction from the state's public

⁴⁶ Richard Baron, 'The Ethics of Taxation' (*Philosophy Now*, Issue 90, 2012) <https://philosophynow.org/issues/90/The_Ethics_of_Taxation> last accessed 9 August 2020; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) Introduction.

⁴⁷ Tuckness Alex, 'Locke's Political Philosophy', *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring edn, 2020) <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2020/entries/locke-political/> last accessed 20 August 2020; John Snape and Jane Frecknall-Hughes, 'John Locke: property, tax and the private sphere' in Peter Harris and Dominic De Cogan (eds), *Studies in the History of Tax Law* (Hart Publishing 2017) 1-35 <[10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001](https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001)> last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁴⁸ Graham A.J. Rogers, 'John Locke' (*Encyclopædia Britannica*, 14 May 2020) <<https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Locke>> last accessed 22 August 2020;

⁴⁹ John Locke, *Second Treatise of Government* (first published 1689, BN Publishing 2008); Edward Andrew, 'Possessive Individualism and Locke's Doctrine on Taxation' (2012) vol 21, no 1 *The Good Society* 151-168 <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5325/goodsociety.21.1.0151>> last accessed 18 August 2020; Edward Andrew, 'Locke on Consent, Taxation and Representation' (2015) vol 62, 2 *Theoria* 15.

⁵⁰ John Snape and Jane Frecknall-Hughes, 'John Locke: property, tax and the private sphere' in Peter Harris and Dominic De Cogan (eds), *Studies in the History of Tax Law* (Hart Publishing 2017) 1-35 <[10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001](https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001)> last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁵¹ *Ibid.*

⁵² *Ibid.*, footnote 50.

sphere. Locke established a modern privacy concept which resulted in the foundation of the private's sphere impregnable character.⁵³

In the TTG2 he expressed that people have a natural and inherent right to property which includes a wide conception of rights: such as those of right to life and liberty;⁵⁴ and, it is perceived, that Locke's property theory is such as to exclude the taxation's role as means of wealth distribution from rich to poor.⁵⁵

Furthermore, according to the Lockean property theory, property rights are characterised as natural and pre-political since they originated prior to the political societies' existence. One of the many legitimate objectives of political societies is their competence to defend and promote natural rights. Thus, any deterioration or relinquishment of these rights, in favour of governments, without the holders' consent is reprehensible. Instead, it must be voluntary; and in case it is forced mandatory, it has to be compensated as an injury to the rights holder.⁵⁶

Last but not least, with the emphasis given to property rights, as well as to the holders' voluntary act and consent to support governments' objectives, Locke accepts that some people, at the time of political societies' creation, took advantage both of their talent and other internal or external factors and had evidently succeeded, more than the rest. Therefore, a "disproportionate and unequal possession" of property rights can be justified. Now it becomes clear that John Locke was arguing about basic equality, not for an equality of outcome.⁵⁷

⁵³ John Snape and Jane Frecknall-Hughes, 'John Locke: property, tax and the private sphere' in Peter Harris and Dominic De Cogan (eds), *Studies in the History of Tax Law* (Hart Publishing 2017) 1-35 <[10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001](https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001)> last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁵⁴ Ibid; Edward Andrew, 'Possessive Individualism and Locke's Doctrine on Taxation' (2012) vol 21, no 1 *The Good Society* 151-168 <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5325/goodsociety.21.1.0151>> last accessed 18 August 2020.

⁵⁵ John Snape and Jane Frecknall-Hughes, 'John Locke: property, tax and the private sphere' in Peter Harris and Dominic De Cogan (eds), *Studies in the History of Tax Law* (Hart Publishing 2017) 1-35 <[10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001](https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001)> last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Ibid, footnote 55; J. Waldron, *God, Locke, and Equality: Christian Foundations of John Locke's Political Thought* (CUP 2002) 151-187; John Snape and Jane Frecknall-Hughes, 'John Locke: property, tax and the private sphere' in Peter Harris and Dominic De Cogan (eds), *Studies in the History of Tax Law* (Hart Publishing 2017) 1-35 <[10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001](https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001)> last accessed 21 August 2020; Edward Andrew, 'Possessive Individualism and Locke's Doctrine on Taxation' (2012) vol 21, no 1 *The Good Society* 151-168 <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5325/goodsociety.21.1.0151>> last accessed 18 August 2020.

Chapter 3

The Evolution of Corporate Tax.

This chapter will offer a cognitive background regarding the role of corporate income tax and the intentions of both the legislators and policy tax maker in the formation, imposition as well as in the maintenance of a corporate level tax on profits. Moreover, we will focus on the evolution of corporate tax over the years as a result of economic and political influence. Thereinafter, we will present an overview of the most prevailing, in tax and economic debates, blueprints for corporate tax reform both in a European and International level.

3.1 The Functions of The Corporate Income Tax

In any discussion of both corporate income tax and its policy, the first question we need to answer is the following: What are the role and the founding principles of corporate tax? Thus, we can lay the keystone for the continuation of the discussion on the intentions of legislators and policymakers for corporate tax reform.

The first of the central traditional answers for imposing a separate tax on corporations lies in the practical difficulties and complexities of both managing and examining the overall capital income tax accruing to any individual. Thus, corporate income tax can substitute a personal tax adequately, since it is feasible and convenient to lay a tax at the corporate level.⁵⁸ However, there is no similarity in the tax rates.⁵⁹

A second explanation of retaining a corporate tax on profits lays, according to many legislators, to the position and meaning of the corporate tax as compensation in exchange for the public goods and services offered by the government in favour of the corporations.⁶⁰ However, a question arises concerning the validity of the above rationale of imposing corporate taxes as a charge for public benefits: Is it feasible to value how much a corporation does benefit from the government's services and then to reflect, such a relation, to a corporate tax burden? Is it even feasible to draw a line of connection between these parameters? Rather it seems that any income tax on corporate level operates like a poorly institutionalised solution of the missing user fees.⁶¹

⁵⁸ V S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, AmJSociol 758,764 https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents last accessed 9 August 2020.

⁵⁹ V S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, AmJSociol 758,764 https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents last accessed 9 August 2020; John Snape and Jane Frecknall-Hughes, 'John Locke: property, tax and the private sphere' in Peter Harris and Dominic De Cogan (eds), *Studies in the History of Tax Law* (Hart Publishing 2017) 1-35 <10.5040/9781509908400.ch-001> last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁶⁰ Ibid, footnote 58.

⁶¹ Ibid, footnote 58

Furthermore, a third answer concerning the existence of corporate tax is theoretically addressed to, relatively, closed economies. Notably, it is suggested that corporate tax is being formulated to a more efficient tax which will be imposed only on economic rent. In that way, it is believed that the economic and general business goals will remain unaffected with fewer distortions for the whole economy. Therefore, such a tax would be a more effective and, politically, attractive means in replacing, in the course, the existent inefficient corporate taxes which deform the economic and business goals by taxing the total return to equity.⁶² Nevertheless, it is empirically proven that the businesses' decision as to whether and where to be incorporated depends on, among others, the taxes, of any form, paid. As a result, in essence, taxes on economic rent are not that neutral, as they are characterised, and can have an impact on investments' planning.

Thereinafter, a fourth rationale underpinning the subsistence of corporate income tax which has positive reception by most of the policymakers and reminds us of significant conceptions of the political philosophy foreground concerning taxation and property, is that corporations are obliged to pay their fair share of tax.⁶³ Undoubtedly, such a concept is popular in political philosophy as well as in the field of politics. However, it is quite ambiguous and incoherent on the ground of economics and company's law, since corporations are legal entities which cannot be subject to a tax burden. Therefore, as a matter of course, the burden of corporate income tax is transferred to the shareholders and individuals, who have a position in a chain reaction which starts with the shareholders and ends to a group of workers, consumers and other investors. As a result, it is perceived that corporate tax is transferred to a group of individuals ahead of companies and shareholders.⁶⁴

Another argument in favour of the corporate-level tax maintenance, which results from the combination of the all above, develops as follows: Legislators and policymakers suggest that by levying corporate taxes, particularly a source-based corporate tax, it is possible to effectively tax rents accruing to non-domestic investors, who take advantage of a government's infrastructure, public services, and business protection.⁶⁵ Taking into account that the economic globalisation inclines to increase the number of corporations owned by foreigners, such a tax is possible to increase the tax revenues by non-domestic investors. Furthermore, such a tax can be used by the government for "national consumption" in political terms by indicating that

⁶² V S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, *AmJSociol* 758,764
https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents last accessed 9 August 2020.

⁶³ *Ibid.*

⁶⁴ Matt Timms, 'Zero Corporation tax: the arguments for and against' (*European Ceo*, 31 December 2014) <<https://www.europeanceo.com/finance/zero-corporation-tax-the-arguments-for-and-against/>> last accessed 12 August 2020; Kevin A. Hassett and Aparna Mathur, 'A spatial model of corporate tax incidence' (2015) 47:13 *Applied Economics* 1350-1365 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2014.995367> last accessed 15 August 2020.

⁶⁵ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 1 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 3 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 6.

foreign investors are, partially, participate in the local economy and pay their share of tax. It is also confirmed by the findings set by Huizing and Nicodème (2003).⁶⁶ They proved, by using comprehensive European data, the close fiscal relationship between corporate tax and the investment and company portfolios owned by foreigners.⁶⁷ Also, R. Musgrave and P. Musgrave, in *Public Finance in Theory and Practice*, situated that a corporate source-based tax, as indicated above, which partially transfer the tax burden to foreign investors, can be used for granting tax equity between different jurisdictions.⁶⁸

Therefore, now we understand why effective corporate tax rates have not fallen sharply. However, their figures are almost stable, despite the rise in capital and profit mobility of recent decades.⁶⁹

We comprehend that the phenomenon of globalisation provides various incentives for the governments to maintain or even, in some occasions, increase their corporate tax, while policymakers and legislators are, continuously, trying to get a step ahead of the regional and international tax competition to attract investments. Undoubtedly, such process operates concurrently with minimising any distortions to corporate's investments and financial planning in their state's territory.⁷⁰

3.2 The Evolution of Corporate Tax in a Globalised Economy

In this section, we will introduce and examine some noticeable trends in corporate tax, during its development across the OECD region.⁷¹ Undoubtedly, income tax on a corporate level is considerably intricate as well as the legislation which accompanies them constitutes complex text imprinted on thousands of pages; the same volume has, also, the case law which corroborates corporate tax law. Therefore, we will lay out a broad but comprehensible depiction

⁶⁶ Harry Huizinga and Gaëtan Nicodème, 'Foreign ownership and corporate taxation: an empirical investigation' (2003) CEPR Discussion Paper 3952.

⁶⁷ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Harry Huizinga and Gaëtan Nicodème, 'Foreign ownership and corporate taxation: an empirical investigation' [2003] CEPR Discussion Paper 3952.

⁶⁸ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Richard A. Musgrave and Peggy B. Musgrave, *Public Finance in Theory and Practice* (5th edn, McGraw-Hill College 1989).

⁶⁹ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Jack Mintz, 'Is there a future for capital income taxation?' (1995) 42 *Canadian Tax Journal* 1469-1503.

⁷⁰ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁷¹ OECD, 'Member Countries' (OECD, April 2020) <<https://www.oecd.org/about/members-and-partners/>> last accessed 18 August 2020.

of the corporate tax development according to both its rates and its influence in OECD countries.

Thereinafter, we will examine and appraise, through figures, the future corporate tax directions with the concurrent analysis of relevant factors which have put pressure and influenced tax rates over the last decades.

The tax competition between jurisdictions in both regional and international level resulted in a “race to the bottom” in the attempt to attract investment and mobile economic activity; mobile capital and profit.⁷² Governments compete with each other to attract investments and establish, both in a short and long term, an economic and business hub. A common way in which they can ulcerate internal and external investments, to achieve their economic aims, is by setting low either the statutory or effective rates, or even, by vanishing the tax on the return to capital located in their jurisdiction. However, it turns out that the common belief which observes the corporate tax downfall, given the effects of globalisation, it is not entirely accurate. It is partly true and accurate because as we will find out, below, on an aggregate scale, corporation tax has been preserved in relatively stable ratios despite the continues economic changes.⁷³

To present a precise reflection of the last decades’ corporate tax development, we accumulated and will represent data, as was gathered by OECD sources and was contained in the economic paper of *The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform* by M. Devereux and P. Sørensen, as presented, in 2016, at the European Commission of European Communities.⁷⁴ Therefore, we will collocate evidence both on corporate tax revenues from 1965 until 2004 for 21 countries, and on statutory and effective tax rates, as well as on the range of the tax base, from 1982 to 2004 for 19 examined countries.

The statutory tax rate is a basic measure of corporate tax and constitutes the rate imposed by legislation on specific taxable income, in a specific period. Nevertheless, the notion of the statutory tax rate is not as straightforward as it might seem, since taxes can be temporary, supplementary or even be special for specific-sized businesses.⁷⁵ Figure A⁷⁶ illustrates the statutory (corporate) tax rate for each of the 19 considered OECD countries for the period from 1982 to 2004. It cites a picture of significant changes over the examined period, and it appears that the statutory corporation tax rates incline downwards in most of the countries, with the only exception to be noted by Ireland and Spain which, in contrast, increased their respective statutory tax rates. Figure A prejudices us for the impact of tax competition between countries.

⁷² Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, ‘The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform’ [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁷³ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, ‘The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform’ [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Figures A-G page 48 -54; Figure G, page 54.

⁷⁴ Ibid, footnote 72.

⁷⁵ Ibid, footnote 72.

⁷⁶ Figure A, page 48

Furthermore, there is available evidence by Devereux, Lockwood and Redoano who support the notion that governments take into consideration other countries' tax rates.⁷⁷

Thereinafter, high tax rates do not necessarily result in high tax revenues. Tax revenues depend, also, on the range of the tax base. Since corporate tax base is a multifaceted concept and can be defined by many different factors, such as allowances, deductions, we measure only depreciation allowances for capital expenditures (for investment in plant and machinery). We will apply the natural measure of the present discounted value (PDV)⁷⁸. Figure B⁷⁹ illustrates some changes in countries' allowances rate for investment in plant and machinery between 1982 and 2004, according to which the allowances are decreased and, thus, the range of the tax base is broadened since these notions are interconnected. On contrary Greece, Spain and Portugal appear to have increased their allowance rates, while the rest five countries seem to have kept their rates stable.

Moreover, effective (corporation) tax rates are the figure of income to be taxed after the application of several available tax breaks; credits, deductions (etc.). In order to evaluate the impact of corporate tax on capital investments we present the measures of an effective marginal tax rate (EMTR).⁸⁰ Similarly, to evaluate the effects of corporation tax on the multinational group of companies (MNGs) choice as to whether and where to locate their place of production, we have to measure, with the application of an effective average tax rate (EATR),⁸¹ the extent to which the pre-tax profits is reduced by tax. Therefore, Figure C⁸² cites the development of EMTR with an EMTR decrease, however not substantial, in most countries examined, signalling a possible profit-maximising ratio of investments. Respectively, in Figure D⁸³ the EATR rose in Ireland and Canada, retained stably in Italy and, almost stable, in Spain, and decreased in the rest countries, signalling the way for investments by MNGs.

In Figure E,⁸⁴ we find the size of the corporate tax revenues from 1965 to 2005, which reference both to total corporate tax revenues across 21 countries and countries' GDP. Similarly, in Figure F,⁸⁵ we present the global corporate tax revenues between the years 2010 and 2017, as a share of total tax revenue and GDP. Regarding Figure E, it illustrates that

⁷⁷ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Michael P. Devereux, Benjamin Lockwood and Michela Redoano, 'Do countries compete over corporate tax rates?' [2004] CEPR Working paper 3400; James Hines, 'Lessons from behavioural responses to international taxation' (1999) 52 National Tax Journal 305-322; Figure G, page 54.

⁷⁸ OpenStax College, *Principles of Economics* (first published 2014, OpenStax College 2017) <<http://cnx.org/contents/69619d2b-68f0-44b0-b074-a9b2bf90b2c6@11.346>> last accessed 10 August 2020.

⁷⁹ Figure B, page 49.

⁸⁰ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Figure C, page 50.

⁸³ Figure D, page 51.

⁸⁴ Figure E, page 52.

⁸⁵ Figure F, page 53.

corporate tax revenues, according to each country' GDP in 196, 1982 and 2004, have significant variations from country to country; once again, we identify effects of tax competition between the 21 examined countries. Besides, regarding Figure F, the global corporation tax revenues have been relatively stable, holding a figure of, approximately 15% to the total GDP.

Furthermore, it is understandable and undeniable that tax revenues are of great significance to governments, especially for those who might face revenues and economic drought. The relation between corporate tax rates and tax revenues provide us with evidence of the relevant economic and tax incentives for investment.⁸⁶

Translating the foregoing evidence from figures A-F, it is indisputable that the influence of both capital and profit mobility, as well as the impact of tax competition, guide the corporate tax rates in a free, rather controlled, fall, which is challenging to prevent as it is driven by globalisation.

It is noteworthy to mention that a series of studies and literature investigates the corporate tax rates "race to bottom" in light of the mobility of economic activities concurrently with the effects of the tax competition.⁸⁷ It is suggested that the fall of the OECD countries' corporate tax rates over the examined periods is a consequence of such globalisation's effects. However, the ever-increasing tight tax rules and measures, such as for the taxation of international flows, are responsible for the tax revenues' stability. Therefore, it is accurate to report that despite the constant challenges, corporate tax rates and corporate tax revenues keep their resilience and stay stable over the years. That is confirmed from the simple fact that governments will not quit from their rights to receive payments and increase their revenues from corporate income tax. Thus, it is feasible to experience a slow tempo reduction of national corporate tax rates, for tax competition reasons, but still to a certain degree.⁸⁸

⁸⁶ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020.

⁸⁷ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Michael P. Devereux, Benjamin Lockwood and Michela Redoano, 'Do countries compete over corporate tax rates?' [2004] CEPR Working paper 3400; Rosanne Altshuler and Timothy J. Goodspeed, 'Follow the Leader? Evidence on European and US Tax Competition' (2014) 43, 4 Public Finance Review 485-504 <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1091142114527781>> last accessed 12 August 2020.

⁸⁸ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Figure G, page 54.

Chapter 4

Multinational Groups of Companies and Tax Avoidance Activities.

Multinational groups of companies (MNGs) who now represent a large part of global trade, benefit in both business and economic terms, implement tax reduction methods and take advantage of double taxation treaties to avoid taxes and secure their high-level profits.⁸⁹ This chapter's content gives insight into the MNGs' perspective regarding their tax avoidance strategies by both taking consideration of the parameters which create a fertile ground for their business practices and examining the most common tax avoidance schemes which giant MNGs have in their "tax avoidance toolkit" to operate in the most tax-efficient way for their interests.

4.1 Factors which Fuel MNGs' Tax Avoidance

It is indisputable that the ever-increasing influence of globalisation together with the transition to an integrating economy result in economic turmoil and reorganisation. Therefore, a continuous economic and tax policy marathon takes place, between countries, for the proper adaptation to the new globalised forefront which will reward them with a prominent position in the new economic order of things.

Simultaneously, the adverse of the digital economy paves the way for the application of the MNGs' tax reduction methods since they have a far greater ability to separate their different functions; such as sales, research and development, support services (etc.). Moreover, the development of information and communication technology (ICT) enables MNGs to operate different remote internet businesses and trade processes in combination with the increasing value of their intangible assets, namely intellectual property rights (IPRs).⁹⁰

⁸⁹ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013)

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019)

<<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, 'Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment' (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048-1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019->09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020; Peter Harris, *Corporate Tax Law: Structure, Policy and Practice* (first published 2013, Corporate Tax Series CUP 2013) and; Miguel Correia, *Taxation of Corporate Groups*, (volume 43, Series on International Taxation, Wolters Kluwer 2013).

⁹⁰ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September

2013)<[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf)>accessed 30 March 2020 and; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, 'Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment' (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048- 1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019->09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020.

Countries are, inevitably, taking part in a constant strategic tax competition by offering different corporate tax rates and advantages to attract investment both from the European Union's member states and third-party countries.⁹¹ Given these elements, MNGs can target suitable, for their interests, tax jurisdictions and apply tax avoidance schemes, accordingly, to operate most efficiently and profitably. Also, they are enabled to adjust in record time both their intra-group structures as well as the location of their business' operations to get a competitive advantage against other commercial and trade competitors.⁹²

Furthermore, other factors which facilitate the MNGs' tax avoidance activities are both the existence of the "separate entity approach"⁹³ for MNGs and the elimination of double taxation. Particularly, a country's tax authority when observes and audits an MNG, it does not

⁹¹ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, 'Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment' (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048-1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019->09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020; Peter Harris, *Corporate Tax Law: Structure, Policy and Practice* (first published 2013, Corporate Tax Series CUP 2013) and; Miguel Correia, *Taxation of Corporate Groups*, (volume 43, Series on International Taxation, Wolters Kluwer 2013).

⁹² Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, 'Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment' (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048-1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019->09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020; Peter Harris, *Corporate Tax Law: Structure, Policy and Practice* (first published 2013, Corporate Tax Series CUP 2013) and; Miguel Correia, *Taxation of Corporate Groups*, (volume 43, Series on International Taxation, Wolters Kluwer 2013).

⁹³ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, 'Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment' (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048-1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019->09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020; Peter Harris, *Corporate Tax Law: Structure, Policy and Practice* (first published 2013, Corporate Tax Series CUP 2013) ; Miguel Correia, *Taxation of Corporate Groups*, (volume 43, Series on International Taxation, Wolters Kluwer 2013); Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of "tax shaming"' (*BBC News Magazine*, 21 May 2013) < <https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359>> accessed 29 March 2020; Jill Treanor, 'Avoiding tax robs our public services, declares minister' (The Guardian, 20 September 2009) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2009/sep/20/tax-avoidance-penalties>> accessed 29 March 2020 and; Joseph Stiglitz, 'Corporate tax avoidance: it's no longer enough to take half measures' (The Guardian, 7 October 2019) < <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2019/oct/07/corporate-tax-avoidance-climate-crisis-inequality>> accessed 27 March 2020; Tommaso Faccio and Sol Picciotto, 'Alternatives to the Separate Entity/Arm's Length Principle for Taxation of Multinational Enterprises' [2017] ICRIFT <<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5a0c602bf43b5594845abb81/t/5a78e704085229b40a97bc01/1517872901804/ICRICT+Alternatives+Eng+Sept+2017.pdf>> last accessed 10 July 2020.

count it as a one and whole entity for tax purposes, as it is required from the “unitary approach”,⁹⁴ but takes into account only the MNGs’ business function which operates in its jurisdiction;⁹⁵ this approach could lead to the double taxation of an MNG’s profit.

Therefore, in the 1920s an international tax regime, based on model OECD and United Nation’s treaties, came into force according to which, until now, more than 2.500 tax agreements have been concluded between countries, across the globe, to eliminate the double taxation of the same profits.⁹⁶ Nevertheless, we must not ignore the fact that countries have different tax policies and strategies to attract investments; for instance, some countries may have significant low tax rates, or even, zero corporate tax, and others may offer several tax breaks.⁹⁷

All of the above, in combination with both the complexity of defining what exactly constitutes “economic activity which generate profit”⁹⁸, “what is a sale and when does it occur”⁹⁹ as well as the difficulty in verifying the original geographical sources of any profits, have formed a favourable environment for the implementation of tax avoidance methods by the multinational group of companies.

⁹⁴ Tommaso Faccio and Sol Picciotto, ‘Alternatives to the Separate Entity/Arm’s Length Principle for Taxation of Multinational Enterprises’ [2017] ICRIFT<<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5a0c602bf43b5594845abb81/t/5a78e704085229b40a97bc01/1517872901804/ICRICT+Alternatives+Eng+Sept+2017.pdf>> last accessed 10 July 2020.

⁹⁵ A concept derived almost a century ago when MNGs were different from what we currently know.

⁹⁶ European Commission, ‘Treaties for the avoidance of double taxation concluded by Member States’ (*European Commission, Taxation and Customs Union*) <https://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/individuals/personal-taxation/treaties-avoidance-double-taxation-concluded-member-states_en> last accessed 20 August 2020.

⁹⁷ Christopher Needham, ‘Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms’ (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, ‘How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research’ (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Martin O’Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 12

⁹⁸ Christopher Needham, ‘Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms’ (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, ‘How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research’ (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, ‘Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment’ (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048-1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019-09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020.

⁹⁹ Tom Bergin, ‘It’s not just Google...’ [2013] Reuters; Foo Yun Chee, ‘EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search’ (*Reuters*, 1 July 2020) <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020.

4.2 *The MNGs' Tax Avoidance Methods*

The tax avoidance methods implemented by the multinational group of companies concern the shifting of profits from high tax jurisdictions to low, or no tax jurisdictions, via the transfer or/and creation of losses both to reduce profits in high tax countries and generate profits in low tax countries respectively. We will present eight central tax avoidance schemes as implemented by major MNGs.¹⁰⁰ Nevertheless, the following presentation is not intended to constitute a manual for tax experts and accountants, rather than give insight into MNGs' business strategies.

4.2.1 *The Strategy of Profit-Shifting and The Permanent Establishment Rules*

This method can be applied by confining MNGs' main operation activities and decreasing income in high tax jurisdictions by transferring them to an affiliate located in a low, or zero, tax jurisdiction. The MNGs achieve profit-shifting through the current double tax treaties and the rules on tax residency, namely the permanent establishment (PE) rules. The PE rules facilitate MNGs to create a business tax base in a low tax jurisdiction, for instance, in Ireland, despite the generation of business in high tax markets, like in Germany. With the MNGs' permanent establishment tax is not paid where the business, primarily, takes place but on where the business is finalised and contracted with consumers since according to the law, permanent establishment indicates a business' tax presence and is defined by whether a company sells in a specific location.¹⁰¹ However, a sale is not considered to taking place when and, in the location, where it is negotiated but when it acquires a legal status through a signed contract.¹⁰² Therefore, many MNGs, by using, the so-called by the OECD, "artificial avoidance of PE status", operate their businesses through their PE and according to its rules.¹⁰³ It is worth noting that, according to Reuters, the 74% of the top 50, by market capitals, US MNGs operating in the fields of software, hardware and internet use their PE structures to avoid tax, with only 13 out of 50 US MNGs declaring their total income in the primary main markets where they generated it.¹⁰⁴

¹⁰⁰ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9; Foo Yun Chee, 'EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search' (Reuters, 1 July 2020) < <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020.

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² Ibid, footnote 100.

¹⁰³ Ibid, footnote 100.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid, footnote 100; Table I, page 59.

4.2.2 The MNGs' Transfer Pricing¹⁰⁵

Transfer pricing is an accounting term for inter-company transactions. It is achieved by, artificially, formulating prices for transactions between companies that belong to the same MNG. Over 50% of global transactions have the form of inter-company transactions.¹⁰⁶ The setting of prices can take place in transactions concerning tangible goods, intangible assets and use of services.¹⁰⁷ To control the arranged prices for intra-group trade, many countries use the so-called “arm's length principle” which indicates that the transaction prices should be the same as it would be if two non-related companies traded with each other.¹⁰⁸ Nevertheless, it is intricate to determine the arm's length prices resulting in the MNGs' freedom to set prices accordingly, as to maintain their tax liabilities at low levels.¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁵ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9; Foo Yun Chee, 'EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search' (Reuters, 1 July 2020) <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020; Kimberly A. Clausing, 'Tax-Motivated Transfer Pricing and US Intrafirm Trade Prices' (2003) 87 9-10 Journal of Public Economics 2207-2223 <[0.1016/S0047-2727\(02\)00015-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2727(02)00015-4)> last accessed 13 August 2020; Ronald Davies, Julien Martin, Mathieu Parenti and Farid Toubal, 'Knocking on Tax Haven's Door: Multinational Firms and Transfer Pricing' [2015] Review of Economics and Statistics.

¹⁰⁶ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9; Foo Yun Chee, 'EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search' (Reuters, 1 July 2020) <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020; Figure 1, page 55.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid.

¹⁰⁸ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020.

¹⁰⁹ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9; Foo Yun Chee, 'EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search'

4.2.3 Corporate Debt Finance.¹¹⁰

Debt financing in the realm of an MNG occurs when company X, located in a low tax jurisdiction with beneficial tax for interests' income (i.e. Luxembourg), grants a loan (even if it is not needed) to a subsidiary -company Y, located in a high tax jurisdiction and company Y pays interest on the loan to company X. The loan's interest constitutes a cost for company Y in the high tax jurisdiction; thus, they reduce its taxable profits, and, respectively, constitute a profit for company X, which is located in a low tax jurisdiction with beneficial tax treatment for interests' income.¹¹¹ Therefore, there is a mismatch of a loan's tax treatment which results in beneficial outcomes for the MNG.

4.2.4 Intangibles' Beneficial Tax Treatment

The payment for intangible assets is a method of MNGs' tax avoidance. It operates as follows: An MNG assigns to one of its affiliates in a favourable tax country for royalties' and licence fees' interest, for instance, the Netherlands, to hold and own all its IPR. Then, the MNG charges its cross-borders affiliates for their use, as to reduce their taxable profits occurring in high tax jurisdictions.¹¹²

(Reuters, 1 July 2020) < <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020.

¹¹⁰ Clemens Fuest, Shafic Hebus and Nadine Riedel, 'International debt shifting and multinational firms in developing economies' (2011) 113 2 Economic Letters 135-138; Thiess Buettner and Georg Wamser, 'Internal Debt and Multinational Profit Shifting: Empirical Evidence From Firm-Level Panel Data' (2013) 66 1 National Tax Journal 63-95.

¹¹¹ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Figure 2, page 56.

¹¹² Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Matthias Dischinger and Nadine Riedel, 'Corporate taxes and the location of intangible assets within multinational firms' (2011) 95 7-8 Journal of Public Economics 691-707; Lisa Evers, Helen Miller and Christoph Spengel, 'Intellectual property box regimes: effective tax rates and tax policy considerations' (2015) 22 3 International Tax and Public Finance 502-530; Figure 3, page 57.

4.2.5 Shell – Parent Companies

A shell company is the one without real business, trade, production and distribution operations; however, it may have centralised financing, licensing and other governance activities.¹¹³ Usually, these companies are holding companies paying dividends and distributing capital gains. They can be traced in low tax jurisdictions, such as in Belgium, the Netherlands, Ireland and Switzerland.

4.2.6 Conduit or Channel Countries.

The MNGs take advantage of these countries as to transfer – channel money and profits through a favourable tax rate. Common examples of such countries, are Mauritius, the Netherlands, Cyprus and the British Virgin Islands (BVI).¹¹⁴

4.2.7 Negotiation of Corporate Tax Rulings

Several countries, such as the Netherlands, Luxembourg and Cyprus allow, queerly, the negotiation of specific tax rules and rates between companies and the domestic tax authority. Undeniably, such a provision is an attractive tool for MNGs.¹¹⁵

4.2.8 Hybrid Entities and the “Double Irish with a Dutch sandwich”

Hybrid entities operate by obtaining tax deductions of the same from two different jurisdictions based on the MNG’s affiliates’ structures. It seems identical to the dual residence companies.¹¹⁶ Besides, the “Double Irish with a Dutch sandwich” is a well-known structure of tax reduction between two wholly-owned subsidiaries with transactions in Ireland, the Netherland and

¹¹³ Christopher Needham, ‘Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms’ (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020.

¹¹⁴ Christopher Needham, ‘Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms’ (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020.

¹¹⁵ Ibid.

¹¹⁶ Christopher Needham, ‘Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms’ (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Martin O’Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 12.

Bermuda. The Irish company has a dual residence, share residence, with Bermuda and transfers profits through a Dutch affiliate back to Bermuda, where profits are not taxed due to Bermuda's zero corporation tax.¹¹⁷

Undoubtedly, the above, sophisticated tax reduction practices have become an art form through which the major business sophisticated multinational groups take advantage of the already fertile economic and tax ground, as it has been created by the effects of globalisation, the adverse of the digital economy and the influence of tax competition. Therefore, they gain an advantage which is not ordinarily available to domestic or to less business-orientated MNGs.

¹¹⁷ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Martin O'Neill and Shepley Orr, *Taxation: Philosophical Perspectives* (OUP 2018) ch 12;; Figure 4, page 58.

The Tide of Public Opinion Against MNGs' Tax Planning.

Taking the baton from the previous chapters, together with the philosophical background regarding the connection of both political philosophy and ethical theories with taxation property and justice, we will analyse the elements composing the current momentum against MNGs' tax planning. Therefore, the current chapter will be divided into two sections as to both examine the growing culture of tax shaming MNGs and provide a discussion on whether MNGs' tax avoidance activities are immoral - unethical, or not.

5.1 *The Momentum Against MNGs' Tax Planning*

The MNGs have long had complex and sophisticated tax structures in order to serve their interests most efficiently and profitably way. However, a recent spate of stories has highlighted several MNGs which use tax avoidance practices and are not seen to be playing their part.¹¹⁸ The publicity and the media constitute a driving force for the development of social feelings against the MNGs' tax planning. Press reports have highlighted not only the low tax paid by giant multinational groups but also revealed some of their reduction schemes which led to a growing culture of naming and shaming the participated, in such activities, MNGs'.¹¹⁹

It is noteworthy to mention that decades ago, in contrast to recent years, information leak and reports of companies reducing their tax liability would have been more likely to be imprinted on the inside business pages of subscription business and economic magazines.

¹¹⁸ Christopher Needham, 'Corporate tax avoidance by multinational firms' (Library Briefing – Library of the European Parliament, 23 September 2013) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI\(2013\)130574_REV1_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2013/130574/LDM_BRI(2013)130574_REV1_EN.pdf) accessed 30 March 2020; Miroslav Palansky, 'How multinationals continue to avoid paying hundreds of billions of dollars in tax – new research' (The Conversation, 3 October 2019) <<https://theconversation.com/how-multinationals-continue-to-avoid-paying-hundreds-of-billions-of-dollars-in-tax-new-research-124323>> accessed 30 March 2020; Petr Jansky and Miroslav Palansky, 'Estimating the scale of profit shifting and tax revenue losses related to foreign direct investment' (2019) 26 Int Tax Public Finance, 1048-1103 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019->09547-8>> accessed 29 March 2020; Peter Harris, *Corporate Tax Law: Structure, Policy and Practice* (first published 2013, Corporate Tax Series CUP 2013); Miguel Correia, *Taxation of Corporate Groups*, (volume 43, Series on International Taxation, Wolters Kluwer 2013); Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of 'tax shaming'' (*BBC News Magazine*, 21 May 2013) <<https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359>> accessed 29 March 2020; Jill Treanor, 'Avoiding tax robs our public services, declares minister' (The Guardian, 20 September 2009) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2009/sep/20/tax-avoidance-penalties>> accessed 29 March 2020 and; Joseph Stiglitz, 'Corporate tax avoidance: it's no longer enough to take half measures' (The Guardian, 7 October 2019) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2019/oct/07/corporate-tax-avoidance-climate-crisis-inequality>> accessed 27 March 2020; Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9; Foo Yun Chee, 'EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search' (*Reuters*, 1 July 2020) <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020;

¹¹⁹ Ibid, footnote 118.

Nowadays, large, legible headings with bold font occupying a prominent position on the covers of many daily newspapers and magazines which prejudice us for a multi-page report on MNGs' tax planning from a social, political and economic aspect.¹²⁰ In a few words, tax planning was a technical concept which only a few people, and experts, knew about.

The MNGs' tax planning becomes a target for activists, anti-cuts campaigners, tax researches, tax experts, international organisations and trade unions. Especially, after the recent investigations of leading, in the digital economy, multinational groups of companies, both by the US Senate Subcommittees and the Commission of Public Accounts in the United Kingdom.¹²¹

The above publicity and the constant investigation, by journalist, of MNGs' tax avoidance schemes led to public awareness. Simultaneously, harsh comments for MNGs' tax planning by prominent politicians created a genuine public frustration due to the assumption that major multinational groups take tax advantages and have a lenient tax treatment by governments which result in unjust tax burdens for taxpayers.¹²² Thus, it was expected that according to Christian Aid's survey, which addressed to the public of Great Britain, the public's anger over tax avoidance activities had been increased significantly.¹²³

¹²⁰ Ibid, footnote 118.

¹²¹ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; The Permanent Subcommittee on Investigations, 'Subcommittee Hearing to Examine Billions of Dollars in U.S. Tax Avoidance By Multinational Corporations' (2012) The Permanent Subcommittee on Investigations <<https://www.hsgac.senate.gov/subcommittees/investigations/media/subcommittee-hearing-to-examine-billions-of-dollars-in-us-tax-avoidance-by-multinational-corporations>> last accessed 21 August 2020; HM Revenue and Customs: Annual Report and Accounts – Public Accounts Committee 'Tax avoidance by multinational companies' (*UK Parliament*, 3 December 2012) <<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201213/cmselect/cmpubacc/716/71605.htm>> last accessed 21 August 2020.

¹²² Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of 'tax shaming'' (*BBC News Magazine*, 21 May 2013) <<https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359>> accessed 29 March 2020; Jill Treanor, 'Avoiding tax robs our public services, declares minister' (*The Guardian*, 20 September 2009) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2009/sep/20/tax-avoidance-penalties>> accessed 29 March 2020 and; Joseph Stiglitz, 'Corporate tax avoidance: it's no longer enough to take half measures' (*The Guardian*, 7 October 2019) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2019/oct/07/corporate-tax-avoidance-climate-crisis-inequality>> accessed 27 March 2020; Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9; Foo Yun Chee, 'EU throws new rule book at Google, tech giants in competition search' (*Reuters*, 1 July 2020) <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-europe-tech-google-antitrust-analysis/eu-throws-new-rule-book-at-google-tech-giants-in-competition-search-idUSKBN242623>> last accessed 21 August 2020; The Permanent Subcommittee on Investigations, 'Subcommittee Hearing to Examine Billions of Dollars in U.S. Tax Avoidance By Multinational Corporations' (2012) The Permanent Subcommittee on Investigations <<https://www.hsgac.senate.gov/subcommittees/investigations/media/subcommittee-hearing-to-examine-billions-of-dollars-in-us-tax-avoidance-by-multinational-corporations>> last accessed 21 August 2020; HM Revenue and Customs: Annual Report and Accounts – Public Accounts Committee 'Tax avoidance by multinational companies' (*UK Parliament*, 3 December 2012) <<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201213/cmselect/cmpubacc/716/71605.htm>> last accessed 21 August 2020.

¹²³ Institute of Business Ethics, 'Tax Avoidance as an Ethical Issue for Business' (*IBE Institute of Business Ethics*, 17 April 2013) <<https://www.ibe.org.uk/resource/tax-avoidance-as-an-ethical-issue-for-business.html>> last accessed 21 August 2020.

Nevertheless, one would wonder: how much efficient are tax naming and shaming? Michael Devereux stated that he would have never thought that shaming is efficient, since, in the recent past, companies would carry on their business and, secondarily, would focus on their reputation's protection.¹²⁴ Furthermore, branding and marketing experts such as Dr Sue Bridgewater agree that if companies receive substantial damage in their reputation, their financial value is, concurrently, damaged since reputation is a key characteristic for a company's competitive presence in the market.¹²⁵ However, it is complex to know and find the effects of tax shaming reflected on a company's balance sheet.

These above, together with Starbucks' voluntary tax payment,¹²⁶ seem to be arguments in favour of the efficiency of tax shaming.¹²⁷ Nevertheless, Dr Stuart Roper stated that tax shaming has not many positive outcomes since the number of people who are actually taking acts against the, participated in tax avoidance, MNGs is relatively low, and the reputational damage can be repaired with a smart marketing and commercial plan.¹²⁸

Lastly, it is undeniable that, in recent years, the momentum against the multinational groups' tax avoidance activities has been growing and it is more than visible that the tide of public opinion is turning.¹²⁹

5.2 An Ethical Analysis of The MNGs' Tax Avoidance Schemes

Based on what has been said in the sub-section 5.1, the public awareness for the application of tax avoidance practices by multinational groups created an ongoing debate of the ethics surrounding the MNGs' tax planning. The ever-increasing public discussions on tax avoidance, and the several talks between politics, banks, MNGs, as well as, between, national tax

¹²⁴ Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of 'tax shaming'' (*BBC News Magazine*, 21 May 2013) <<https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359>> accessed 29 March 2020; Jill Treanor, 'Avoiding tax robs our public services, declares minister' (*The Guardian*, 20 September 2009) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2009/sep/20/tax-avoidance-penalties>> accessed 29 March 2020 and; Joseph Stiglitz, 'Corporate tax avoidance: it's no longer enough to take half measures' (*The Guardian*, 7 October 2019) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2019/oct/07/corporate-tax-avoidance-climate-crisis-inequality>> accessed 27 March 2020;

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ A voluntary tax payment, undeniably, undermines the character, nature and the validity of taxation; Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of 'tax shaming'' (*BBC News Magazine*, 21 May 2013) <<https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359>> accessed 29 March 2020.

¹²⁷ Ibid.

¹²⁸ Ibid, footnote 126.

¹²⁹ Ibid, footnote 124.

authorities and international organisations attributed a moral dimension to taxation.¹³⁰ Therefore the ethics of tax avoidance has entered the academic debate.¹³¹

Almost a decade ago, a series of UK judicial rulings wide accepted and reinforced that tax avoidance was not a moral issue.¹³² In particular, in the famous case of *Duke of Westminster v. Inland Revenue Commissioners* (1936) AC 1 19, it was stated that everyone has the right to arrange his, or her, tax affairs in a way as to reduce the tax burden to the burden, initially, attached to him, or her, according to the Act.¹³³ Even though the case law is referred to tax avoidance activities by individuals, in contrast to our dissertation's concentration, we should translate these important rulings as if referred to corporations, since a group of executive managers, tax experts, and corporate tax attorneys, professionally advice companies for the implementation of such schemes.¹³⁴

Thereinafter, according to literature, we will introduce, below, four primary persuasive arguments, from which other flow, which indicated that the MNGs' tax avoidance practices could be ethically defended.

5.2.1 Tax Is A Legal Issue

First of all, an argument in favour of tax avoidance is that tax is a legal and not a moral issue. Taxpayers must comply with the law and their duty does not extend to an obligation of obeying the "spirit" of law or a Parliament's real "intentions".¹³⁵ The law is what the relevant Act indicates, and, in case of doubts, what Courts interprets. Moreover, taxpayers are not

¹³⁰ Institute of Business Ethics, 'Tax Avoidance as an Ethical Issue for Business' (*IBE Institute of Business Ethics*, 17 April 2013) <<https://www.ibe.org.uk/resource/tax-avoidance-as-an-ethical-issue-for-business.html>> last accessed 21 August 2020; Jill Treanor, 'Avoiding tax robs our public services, declares minister' (*The Guardian*, 20 September 2009) <<https://www.theguardian.com/business/2009/sep/20/tax-avoidance-penalties>> accessed 29 March 2020; Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 *Business & Professional Ethics Journal* 53-88; ActionAid, 'Addicted to tax havens: The secret life of the FTSE 100' (*ActionAid UK*, October 2011) <https://www.actionaid.org.uk/sites/default/files/doc_lib/addicted_to_tax_havens.pdf> last accessed 12 August 2020.

¹³¹ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 *Business & Professional Ethics Journal* 53-88; Don R. Hansen, Rick L. Crosser and Doug Laufer, 'Moral ethics v. tax ethics: The case of transfer pricing among multinational corporations' (1992) 11 *Journal of Business Ethics* 679-686; J. Freedman, 'Interpreting Tax Statutes: Tax avoidance and the Intention of Parliament' (2007) 123 *LQR* 53-90;

¹³² Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 *Business & Professional Ethics Journal* 53-88; *Ayrshire Pullman Motor Services v. Commissioners* (1929) 14 TC 754; *Helvering v. Gregory* (1934) 69 F. (2d) 809,810 (C. C. A 2nd 1934); *Duke of Westminster v. Inland Revenue Commissioner* (1936) AC 1 19.

¹³³ *Duke of Westminster v. Inland Revenue Commissioner* (1936) AC 1 19.

¹³⁴ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 *Business & Professional Ethics Journal* 53-88;

¹³⁵ J. Freedman, 'Interpreting Tax Statutes: Tax avoidance and the Intention of Parliament' (2007) 123 *LQR* 53-90; Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 *Business & Professional Ethics Journal* 53-88.

responsible for any tax anomalies and loopholes in the law, but, in contrast, responsible are both the politicians and the legislators.

As a result, in the hypothesis that the MNGs are immoral to take advantage of both the tax loopholes and tax breaks that can be found in tax legislation, then, under the same reasoning, politicians the draftsmanship and governments are surely more immoral for creating such tax loopholes and ambiguities in the first place for providing tax incentives, to, among others, MNGs, in the context and course of the international tax competitions.¹³⁶ In fact, in several jurisdictions, the tax codes are ambiguous and complex, which results in a further burden for multinational groups who want to comply with the law.

Moreover, Hansen, Crosser and Lafer argue that even in the case of an extreme moralist, it could not be accepted for any taxpayer to opt-in for the costliest tax election.¹³⁷ Last but not least, Barry Bracewells-Milnes identified an ethical issue for a taxpayer applying tax avoidance methods. He raised a question: in the assumption that tax avoidance is the morally wrong act, then what is morally right for a taxpayer to do? Would it be to maximise his tax liabilities following the ambiguous, or, in many cases, unknown, intentions of the parliament, or even to search for the “spirit” of the law in the Act? The answer is clearly “no”. No one would ever suggest that.¹³⁸ A taxpayer has no moral obligation to look beyond the words in the Act since the only way for a Parliament to express its intentions is through the legislative procedures and its legislative outcomes.¹³⁹

5.2.2 *The Government’s Intervention to the Private Sphere: A Rather Libertarian Argument*

According to this line of reasoning, some libertarians would suggest, not only, that tax avoidance is wholly ethical but, also, would challenge the existence and nature of taxes.¹⁴⁰ Barker, finds an “ideology” foundation in favour of tax avoidance;¹⁴¹ tax avoidance can be

¹³⁶ Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, ‘Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of ‘tax shaming’’(BBC News Magazine, 21 May 2013) < <https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359> > accessed 29 March 2020.

¹³⁷ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; Don R. Hansen, Rick L. Crosser and Doug Laufer, ‘Moral ethics v. tax ethics: The case of transfer pricing among multinational corporations’ (1992) 11 Journal of Business Ethics 679-686.

¹³⁸ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88.

¹³⁹ Ibid.

¹⁴⁰ See chapter 2; Robert Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (New York: Basic Books 1974); John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (HUP 1999) < <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctvkjb25m> > last accessed 23 August 2020; Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88.

¹⁴¹ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; William B. Barker, ‘The

defended by the right of freedom through which a taxpayer coexist harmonically with a minimum government which does not interfere to his, or her, private sphere.¹⁴²

5.2.3 Governments' Policy and Incompetence in Allocating Their Tax Proceeds

Another argument emphasising the defense of tax avoidance practices relates to the inability of a government to use its tax revenues efficiently as to serve the common good.¹⁴³ In other words, if tax revenues going towards the support of immoral activities, or are used for the promotion of pork-barrel legislation, then tax avoidance can be justified on moral grounds. The final use and the way according to which the proceeds from tax revenues are utilised have a close relation to the ethics of tax avoidance.¹⁴⁴ Such a close connection is confirmed by taking into account that in countries where the government is linked with corruption and tax inefficiencies, the taxpayers are more reluctant to pay their tax liabilities.¹⁴⁵

5.2.4 Managerial Fiduciary and Professional Duties

Thereinafter, the fourth line of reasoning is situated in the assumption that the corporate executives and the corporation's professional experts are "agents" and obliged by fiduciary and professional duties. They accept to operate in ways to satisfy their "principals'" interests, namely the interest of the shareholders, workers, and other stakeholders. Thus, they work in order to both minimise the company's tax liabilities and maximise its profits by taking advantage of the available legal means, on the claim that their methods are sound business practices.¹⁴⁶ It is notable that several MNGs, such as Vodafone, have a code of conduct and have recognised the business practices in which they maximise the company's value in all legal means.¹⁴⁷

Ideology of Tax Avoidance' (2009) 40(1) Loyola University Chicago Law Journal 229-251

<<http://lawcommons.luc.edu/luclj/vol40/iss2/3> last accessed 10 August 2020.

¹⁴² Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; William B. Barker, 'The Ideology of Tax Avoidance' (2009) 40(1) Loyola University Chicago Law Journal 229-251

<<http://lawcommons.luc.edu/luclj/vol40/iss2/3> last accessed 10 August 2020.

¹⁴³ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88.

¹⁴⁴ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88.

¹⁴⁵ Ibid.

¹⁴⁶ Don R. Hansen, Rick L. Crosser and Doug Laufer, 'Moral ethics v. tax ethics: The case of transfer pricing among multinational corporations' (1992) 11 Journal of Business Ethics 679-686; Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of 'tax shaming''(BBC News Magazine, 21 May 2013) <<https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359>> accessed 29 March 2020.

¹⁴⁷ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. 'State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices' (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; Vodafone Group Plc,

Last but not least, on the question of whether accountants, solicitors, barristers and other professionals should be penalized for aiding and promoting tax avoidance schemes for the interests of their clients, the answer is negative. Because, not only they operate in the context of their studies, profession and experiences and offer their knowledge when it is required, but, it is, also, safe to say that the vast majority of their professional codes of conduct condemn neither the advice nor the application of tax avoidance schemes.¹⁴⁸

‘Vodafone Group Plc Tax Strategy (*Vodafone*, 31 March 2019) <<https://www.vodafone.com/content/dam/vodcom/sustainability/pdfs/tax-strategy-2018.pdf>> last accessed 13 August 2020.

¹⁴⁸ Michael Blackwell, ‘Warning solicitors against aiding tax avoidance risks undermining the rule of law’ (*The New York Times*, 26 March 2019) <<https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/warning-solicitors-against-aiding-tax-avoidance-is-risks-undermining-the-rule-of-law-pqftp5gwc>> last accessed 28 August 2020; Michael Blackwell, ‘Conduct Unbefitting: Solicitors, the SRA and Tax Avoidance’ (2019) n1 *British Tax Review* 31-54; Solicitors Regulation Authority, ‘Warning notice on Tax avoidance – your duties’ (*SRA*, updated 25 November 2019) <<https://www.sra.org.uk/solicitors/guidance/tax-avoidance-duties/>> last accessed 28 August 2020.

Chapter 6

Tax Avoidance v. Tax Evasions; Arguments in Favour of the MNGs' Tax Avoidance Activities.

The current chapter will explore the notions of tax avoidance and tax evasion and will clarify the differences between these two opposite tax practices. Thereinafter, the following part will focus on introducing arguments in favour of tax avoidance and their implementation by MNGs.

6.1 The Notions of Tax Avoidance and Tax Evasion

According to the Oxford dictionary, tax avoidance is “the arrangement of one’s financial affairs to minimise tax liability within the law”.¹⁴⁹ OECD states that “avoidance is a term that is difficult to define”¹⁵⁰ since there is no commonly established definition of tax avoidance. However, a comprehensive definition of tax avoidance develops as follows: tax avoidance is the artificial way of arrangement, to minimise, of a taxpayer’s financial affairs, tax burden, by exploiting, without deliberate deception, tax rules and loopholes occurring as a result of tax competition between countries. These arrangements can evolve into complex corporate structures. Tax avoidance is not based on the concealment of information but is based on various strategic business transactions. The arrangements of a taxpayer’s affairs are utterly legal since they comply with the letter of the law; usually, in contradiction with the “spirit” of law and a Parliament’s “intentions”.

As we have presented, in previous chapters, in more recent years the momentum against tax avoidance activities and the ongoing debates of the ethics on the legitimacy of MNGs’ tax avoidance created a negative cloak surrounding the concept of this tax practice. As a result, tax avoidance has been linked with the illegal tax practice of tax evasion and, is, still, described as “abusive”¹⁵¹ and “evil”¹⁵².¹⁵³ It is noteworthy to mention that the Confédération Fiscale Européenne (CFE)¹⁵⁴ expressed its concerns about the European Court of Justice (ECJ)

¹⁴⁹ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88.

¹⁵⁰ Ibid.

¹⁵¹ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; HMRC, ‘A General Anti-Abuse Rule Consultation Document’ (UK HMRC, 12 June 2012) <http://www.hmrc.gov.uk/avoidance/gaar.htm> last accessed 19 August 2020.

¹⁵² Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88

¹⁵³ Ibid.

¹⁵⁴ Asociación Española de Asesores Fiscales, ‘Confédération Fiscale Européenne’ (aeDAF) <<https://www.aedaf.es/en/about-aedaf/cfe-tax-advisors-127>> last accessed 17 August 2020.

practices to refer to terms such as “abusive of law”, “abusive of rights” and “abusive of practices” in cases concerned with tax avoidance activities.¹⁵⁵

In light of the above, and due to the mistaken terminological confusion regarding the tax practice of tax avoidance, we will continue our work with explaining the concept of tax evasion to clarify its fundamental differences with tax avoidance.

The notion of tax evasion and its implementation methods have been at the center of discussions for many years, and literature embodies many definitions of tax evasion’s practice.¹⁵⁶ In alignment with the definition of tax evasion offered by the OECD, tax evasion is “generally used to mean illegal arrangements where liability to tax is hidden or ignored, i.e. the taxpayer pays less tax than he is legally obligated to pay by hiding income or information from the tax authorities”.¹⁵⁷ Tax evasion is a criminal offence, and those who engage with its practices face the risk of prosecution.

However, that is not the case for the tax reduction methods which multinational groups of companies employ to operate in the most and efficient way from both an economic and governance perspective.¹⁵⁸

6.2 Arguments in Favour of Tax Avoidance and the Anomalies of the International Tax System

Bearing in mind the characteristics of tax avoidance and the fundamental contrasts with tax evasion, we will provide arguments in favour of tax avoidance to clarify its misunderstood legality and morality.

To begin with, many scholars, researches and legislators support that tax avoidance is an unethical and wrong act. According to them, those who engage in this tax practice avoid of giving up a property that potentially belongs to others, mainly to the government, and simultaneously, they are taking property to which they have no rights; as a result, those engaging in tax avoidance transfer the tax burden to others who have been deprived of their property.¹⁵⁹

¹⁵⁵ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88; *Halifax plc, Leeds Permanent Development Services Ltd, County Wide Property Investments Ltd v. Commissioners of Customs & Excise* (2006) ECJ Case C-255/02; *Cadbury Schweppes plc & Cadbury Schweppes Overseas Ltd v. Commissioners of Inland Revenue* (2006) ECJ Case C-196/04.

¹⁵⁶ J. Kellough QC, ‘Tax Avoidance 1945-1995’ (1995) 43 Canadian Tax Journal 1819-1843; J. Hasseldine and G. Morris, ‘Corporate Social Responsibility and Tax Avoidance: A Comment and Reflection’ (2013) 37 Accounting Forum 1-14.

¹⁵⁷ Simone de Colle and Ann Marie Bennet. ‘State-induced, Strategic, or Toxic? An Ethical Analysis of Tax Avoidance Practices’ (2014) 33 1 Business & Professional Ethics Journal 53-88.

¹⁵⁸ Chapter 4.

¹⁵⁹ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 3 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020;

However, is it possible to slightly change the components of this view? We could have suggested that taxation is theft and tax avoidance is the action of preventing such an unethical action; or, how is it possible for such an argument to be valid when tax avoidance is taking place in alignment with the law? It is known that theft takes place when someone takes someone away, by force, from his property and the rights embodied in it. Therefore, what about when governments perform this act of expulsion from one's property? Does it constitute theft? Or it is still called taxation? It could be argued that it is governments and not the MNGs and individual taxpayers engaging in tax avoidance, who are taking people's property without their consent but with force and the threat of sanctions. Furthermore, those who pay taxes have no claims on any proceeds; they have no voice on how these proceeds are going to be used. Instead, tax revenues are going into the government's common pool and are distributed as the government decides.¹⁶⁰

Given the preceding, there is no moral duty for the MNGs to pay their tax share, especially when their property can be relinquished by force.¹⁶¹ Moreover, it should not be subject to discussions whether there is morality, or not, in taxation since morality includes choice. When there is no choice, as in the case of taxation, there is no morality.¹⁶² Therefore, tax avoidance can be justified.

However, one might argue that taxation is not coercive and is not accompanied by threats and force since, in the past, people have voted and expressed their consent on taxation. This line of reasoning is phony: Firstly, taxpayers expressed their consent, via voting, in the past. According to the common law, one person cannot be held for a contract of another. Thus, the contract is void as far as those who did not consent, never took place in such negotiations (voting procedures).¹⁶³ Then, from a philosophical perspective, if we accept the hypothesis that some people expressed their consent in taxation through voting procedures, and therefore they bind the other persons, this is standing on a shaky ground philosophically. There is no social contract, and consequently, governments cannot bind those who have never agreed, in their terms, with such justification.¹⁶⁴

Thereinafter, the government is committed to protecting all citizens from securing their right to property, privacy and freedom. Thus, if some taxpayers, due to their talents or devotion

¹⁶⁰ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020;

¹⁶¹ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020;

Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 10 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020;

¹⁶² Ibid, footnote 159.

¹⁶³ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 3 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Thomas Jefferson, *Writings: Autobiography, Notes on the State of Virginia, Public and Private Papers, Addresses, Letters* (Library of America 1984) 959; Thomas Jefferson, *Writings: Autobiography, Notes on the State of Virginia, Public and Private Papers, Addresses, Letters* (Library of America 1984) 1280-1281.

¹⁶⁴ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 3 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020

at work, take an economic lead compared to others, it is wrong if governments impose a higher tax burden to them than to others. Such tax policies seem to both punish the more talented and hard-working taxpayers as well as weakens any incentives for labour, development and thrift.¹⁶⁵ In short, the private sector and its beneficial operations for the general good are suppressed.

Simultaneously, the financially affluent taxpayers, notwithstanding their extensive tax burden over their income, they do not receive financial security nor property protection.¹⁶⁶ They are given no guarantee that in return of paying a large sum of taxes, they are entitled to economic security. Therefore, their entire capital is in danger in the event of adverse business conditions and the only way to counterbalance such financial risks is to seek protection by exploring different available tax regimes and engaging in tax avoidance methods concerning existent tax advantages in the international tax map.¹⁶⁷ Undoubtedly, that is the case for MNGs, since they fail to see whether their tax payments provide the required financial security and property protection. This uncertainty is forcing them to engage in tax avoidance activities due to governments' incompetence in protecting their interests.

Besides, it is suggested that governments operate to provide essential services to the public in the course of restoring inequalities. Therefore, one could argue that governments are the servants of people who are the masters.¹⁶⁸ However, it seems that governments have forgotten their primary role as servants, and they govern as being masters by forcibly intervening in the private sphere;¹⁶⁹ instead of offering requisite services, they demand a large sum of taxes. The governments, to the detriment of others, seem incompetent to operate in a manner other than promoting their interests. As a result, neither the government nor the country, but the private sector and mainly the economic affluent natural and legal persons bear the most significant weight for restoring the prosperity of the society. It is verified by two statistics, which took place in California and Britain, contrary to the general perception, that the tax burden falls unfairly to the small group of wealthy natural and legal persons who hold a prominent position at the top of the high incomes' scale.¹⁷⁰ These findings reflect that governments are exploiting the wealthy minority as to gain the trust of the less wealthy majority and manipulate their decision by the vote's power. In reality, the public services, the goods and economic opportunities instead of being available to the public by the government are offered

¹⁶⁵ V.S Yarros 'Taxation and the Philosophy of the State' (1899) Vol 4, No 6, AmJSocial 758,764
https://www.jstor.org/stable/2761860?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents last accessed 9 August 2020.

¹⁶⁶ Ernest O. Eisenberg, 'The Changing Philosophy of Taxation' [1934] 18 1 MarqLRev.

¹⁶⁷ Ibid.

¹⁶⁸ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2
<<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020.

¹⁶⁹ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2
<<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020; Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 12<<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020.

¹⁷⁰ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 2
<<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020

by the wealthy private sector, which is also persecuted with high taxes and threats. Besides, taxpayers are receiving a smaller distributive amount from tax revenues to what they have paid due to governments' administrative costs.¹⁷¹ Undeniably, the only way of rectifying the altered and confused roles of the governments is the empowerment of the private sector; privatisation. The essential services, goods, and, of all kind, opportunities will be offered in better quality and lesser cost, free of the governments' intervention and coercive monopoly.¹⁷²

Governments are the real thorn in the attempt of flourishing the economy and the general prosperity of the society as a whole.¹⁷³ In the absence of private initiatives, it would be scary to think about the possible consequences for the economic and social quality of life. Therefore, on moral grounds, tax avoidance activities implemented by MNGs should be completely justified. The results of tax reduction practices entail a series of positive outcomes for a society which are often deliberately undermined.

Furthermore, another reason in favour of the MNGs' tax avoidance activities concerns the prevailing competitive tax environment. Countries started to be more competitive to both attract foreign investment and empower the national economy by favourably reforming their tax policy and corporate regulations. They offer tax advantages and business initiatives after first having already considered the existing tax policies in the vast international tax scene. Two papers, the first by Altshuler and Goodspeed (2002) and the other by Devereux, Lockwood and Redoano (2004) cite that governments in order to offer an attractive financial package to potential stakeholders interested in investing, they examine the already corporate and tax regimes of other countries.¹⁷⁴

Therefore, since governments adjust their fiscal policy to lead in this tax competition, MNGs identify and take into account these signals and freely choose when and where to invest their money. In practice, they "shop around" for a proper tax environment, or a combination of tax regimes, to satisfy their business needs and ambitions, avoiding oppressive tax jurisdictions which pose risks to their sustainability.¹⁷⁵ In other words, as a result of globalisation, the economies are becoming borderless in the view of investments' adverse.¹⁷⁶ It is apparent, that since the trade and business barriers fall, MNGs can take legitimate advantage of an increasing number of favourable tax opportunities.

¹⁷¹ Ibid.

¹⁷² Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 12 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020

¹⁷³ F A Hayek, *The Case Against Progressive Income Tax* (The Freeman 1953) 229-232; J Freedman, 'Interpreting Tax Statutes: Tax avoidance and the Intention of Parliament' (2007) 123 LQR 53-90.

¹⁷⁴ Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020; Michael P. Devereux, Benjamin Lockwood and Michela Redoano, 'Do countries compete over corporate tax rates?' [2004] CEPR Working paper 3400; James Hines, 'Lessons from behavioural responses to international taxation' (1999) 52 National Tax Journal 305-322.

¹⁷⁵ Robert W. McGee, *The Philosophy of Taxation and Public Finance*, (Springer 2004) ch 12 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9140-9>> last accessed 23 August 2020

¹⁷⁶ Ibid.

A question arises. Why are private parties, such as MNGs, subject to fines and harsh social criticism when their tax planning is in alignment with the available tax regimes, but when governments do the same thing by fixing their rates it is perfectly legal?¹⁷⁷ Public officers answer that the government's tax planning is taking place in the common interest. Nevertheless, their argument has several flaws. How is it possible to be done in the public interest when high taxes result in a long line of effects? For instance, there are high prices for products, high costs for services and less economic opportunities. In contrast, the MNGs engaging in tax avoidance activities are trying to keep the costs low and secure jobs as well as to ensure good quality products and services. Quaintly, accord to the governments' lenses, their business operations are still illegal and immoral.

¹⁷⁷ Ibid, footnote 173.

Concluding Remarks.

In the current dissertation, the introduction of the taxations' political, economic and social aspects as was underpinned both by the presented political philosophy and the ethics of taxation highlighted common essential points, concerning taxation, from different streams of political philosophy. They affirmed that any government's intervention in the private sphere of taxpayers should not take place arbitrarily and inexhaustibly for the common good, or ostensibly for the common good, which, nevertheless, serves the interests of the governments. Thereinafter, according to the evolution of corporate tax and its current functions in comparison with those of the past, it is proved that the founding principles of corporate tax are no longer valid. The current functions of corporate tax serve the interests of the government and are exploited for manipulative political reasons. The wealthy minority, through taxation, "has been placed" in the eye of the storm, although it contributes substantially to the prosperity of the public and complements the government's welfare provisions.

The MNGs have been targeted by media, politics and other taxpayers due to their sophisticated methods of tax planning. However, none of the above, ever considered which are the reasons which fuel such activities to take place. In reality, the MNGs are taking advantage of the current international tax competition, which prevails between countries who compete in order to become a financial and investment hub. The tax avoidance schemes implemented by the MNGs are entirely in alignment with the law and the domestic tax regulations and policies. Tax avoidance cannot be compared to tax evasion, because these tax practices are distinguished, and the inherent purpose of implementing them are entirely different. Governments should take into consideration the benefits of the private sector and should not interfere with its operations. Bloated welfare countries intervening to the business operations of MNGs are distorting the national economy. As a consequence, the emergence of dangers in the commercial, economic and social balances. Interventionist governments should decrease their welfare character and empower the private sector to accentuate the private incentives for the benefit of the public. However, until these fiscal and political reshuffles take place, the MNGs should not be threatened with sanctions and social condemnations. At any rate, according to the dissertation, the tax avoidance activities as implemented by the MNGs have to be observed and be treated as lawful methods of tax planning which coexist with the current national and international tax regimes. Last but not least, as it seems this dissertation is delivered in a period in which both the announcement of the managing director of Starbucks UK, Kris Engskov, for voluntary tax payments gains ground in the current tax debates and the recent judgement of the General Court of European Union (GCEU), which annulled the decision issued by the European Commission against Ireland and Apple, triggers a new perception of the MNG's tax planning concerning the status of the tax regimes.¹⁷⁸

¹⁷⁸ Vanessa Barford and Gerry Holt, 'Google, Amazon, Starbucks: The rise of 'tax shaming'' (*BBC News Magazine*, 21 May 2013) < <https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-20560359> > accessed 29 March 2020; Simon Neville and Jill Treanor, 'Starbucks to pay £20m in tax over two years after customer revolt' (*The Guardian*, 6 December 2012) <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2012/dec/06/starbucks-to-pay-10m-corporation-tax> last accessed 12 August 2020; Maisto e Associati, 'EU TAX ALERT 2020/09: The Apple case decision on State Aid: The General Court annuls the decision issued by the European Commission against Apple and Ireland' (Maisto e Associati, 15 July 2020) <https://www.maisto.it/en/newsletter/eu-tax-alert--96.html> last accessed 12 August 2020; Case T-778/16 *Ireland and Others v. European Commission* [2016] ECLI:EU:T:2020:338; Case T-892/16 *Apple Sales International and Apple Operations Europe v. European Commission* [2016] ECLI:EU:T:2017:926-925.

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Appendix A

Figure A.
Statutory Corporate Tax Rates
1982-2004

Australia	1.
Austria	2.
Belgium	3.
Canada	4.
Finland	5.
France	6.
Germany	7.
Greece	8.
Ireland	9.
Italy	10.
Japan	11.
Netherlands	12.
Norway	13.
Portugal	14.
Spain	15.
Sweden	16.
Switzerland	17.
United Kingdom	18.
United States of America	19.

1982
2004

Notes

- For countries using different tax rates, the manufacturing rate is chosen.
- Local taxes (or the average across regions) are included where they exist.
- Any supplementary taxes are included only if they apply generally, rather than only under particular circumstances.
- Data for Denmark and Luxembourg are missing.

Source: Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020

Appendix A

Figure B.
Present Discounted Value (PDV) of Depreciation allowances
1982-2004

Australia	1.
Austria	2.
Belgium	3.
Canada	4.
Finland	5.
France	6.
Germany	7.
Greece	8.
Ireland	9.
Italy	10.
Japan	11.
Netherlands	12.
Norway	13.
Portugal	14.
Spain	15.
Sweden	16.
Switzerland	17.
United Kingdom	18.
United States of America	19.

1982
2004

Notes

- Estimates the PDV of allowances for investment in plant and machinery.
- Special 1st year allowances are included where applicable.
- The nominal discount rate is 13.9%, based on inflation of approximately 3.5% and a real discount rate of 10%.
- Data for Denmark and Luxembourg are missing.

Source: Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020

Appendix A

Figure C.
Effective Marginal Tax Rates (EMTR)
1982-2004

Australia	1.
Austria	2.
Belgium	3.
Canada	4.
Finland	5.
France	6.
Germany	7.
Greece	8.
Ireland	9.
Italy	10.
Japan	11.
Netherlands	12.
Norway	13.
Portugal	14.
Spain	15.
Sweden	16.
Switzerland	17.
United Kingdom	18.
United States of America	19.

1982
2004

Notes

- Estimates the development of EMTR over time.
- Figure C follows the approach of Figure B by keeping inflation constant across years and all countries examined.
- Calculations based on a hypothesis: investment for one period in plant and machinery.
- Investment financed by equity or retained profits.
- Data for Denmark and Luxembourg are missing.

Source: Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020

Appendix A

Figure D.
Effective Average Tax Rates (EATR)
1982-2004

Australia	1.
Austria	2.
Belgium	3.
Canada	4.
Finland	5.
France	6.
Germany	7.
Greece	8.
Ireland	9.
Italy	10.
Japan	11.
Netherlands	12.
Norway	13.
Portugal	14.
Spain	15.
Sweden	16.
Switzerland	17.
United Kingdom	18.
United States of America	19.

1982
2004

Notes

- Estimates the development of EATR over time.
- Figure D follows the approach of Figure C & B by keeping inflation constant across years and countries examined.
- Calculations based on a hypothesis: investment for one period in plant and machinery.
- Investment financed by equity or retained profits.
- The expected rate of economic profits earned is 10%.
- Taxation at the shareholder level is not included.
- The EATR depends more on the statutory tax rate than on allowances.
- Data for Denmark and Luxembourg are missing.

Source: Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020

Appendix A

Figure E.
Corporation Tax Revenue as a Proportion of GDP for Each Country.
1965 - 1982 - 2004

Australia	1.
Austria	2.
Belgium	3.
Canada	4.
Denmark	5.
Finland	6.
France	7.
Germany	8.
Greece	9.
Ireland	10.
Italy	11.
Japan	12.
Luxembourg	13.
Netherlands	14.
New Zealand	15.
Norway	16.
Spain	17.
Sweden	18.
Switzerland	19.
United Kingdom	20.
United States of America	21.

Notes

- Estimates the corporation tax revenue % of each country's GDP.
- Differences in country size as well as in the corporate and market sector, are making the comparison of corporate income tax revenues quite challenging. However, a convenient way to calculate and compare the corporate tax revenues is comparing by GDP in each examined country.
- All taxes levied on profits.
- Capital gains of corporations are included.
- Data for Portugal is missing.
- Source: OECD

Source: Michael P. Devereux and Peter Birch Sørensen, 'The Corporate Income Tax: international trends and options for fundamental reform' [2006] Economic Paper 264 http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/index_en.htm last accessed 21 August 2020

Appendix A

Figure F.
Global (Average) Corporation Tax Revenue as a share of Total Tax Revenue and GDP.
2010 - 2017

Notes

- Estimates the global average corporation tax revenues in relation to Total Tax Revenue and GDP.
- These averages are unweighted (averages are calculated in a manner that every arithmetic element has the same weight)
- Source: OECD

Source: Daniel Bunn, 'Decades in Corporate Taxation: Trends in Corporate Revenues and Rate' (*Tax Foundation*, 8 July 2020) <https://taxfoundation.org/decades-corporate-taxation-global-minimum-tax/> last accessed 19 August 2020.

Appendix A

Figure G.
Global (Average) Corporation Tax Rates.
2010 – 2020

Notes

- Estimates the global average corporation tax rates.
- Average combined statutory corporate tax rates.
- Corporate tax rates have been relatively stable.
- These averages are unweighted (averages are calculated in a manner that every arithmetic element has the same weight)

Source: Daniel Bunn, ‘Decades in Corporate Taxation: Trends in Corporate Revenues and Rate’ (*Tax Foundation*, 8 July 2020) <https://taxfoundation.org/decades-corporate-taxation-global-minimum-tax/> last accessed 19 August 2020.

Appendix B

Figure 1.
Transfer Pricing

A multinational group of companies (AB) composed of two companies. Company A located in Australia – a high tax jurisdiction and Company B located in the British Virgin Islands (BVI) – a low tax jurisdiction.

	Corporate Tax Rate %	
Australia	30%	From every \$ shifted from Australia to BVI, the MNG avoids paying 30% of tax.
British Virgin Islands (BVI)	0%	

If Co A wanted to sell suits in Co C for US\$ 100, it would make a profit of US \$20 and pay US\$ 6 in tax (30% Australia). However, using the above scheme, the Co pays only US\$ 0,3 tax and the MNG avoids paying US\$ 5,7 tax in Australia for every product sold.

Source: Deloitte, 'Corporate-Tax Rates 2020' (Deloitte, 2020) <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/global/Documents/Tax/dtl-tax-corporate-tax-rates.pdf> last accessed 12 August 2020.

Appendix B

Figure 2
Corporate Debt Finance.

A multinational group of companies (AB) composed of two companies. Company A located in Australia – a high tax jurisdiction and Company B located in Luxembourg – a favourable tax jurisdiction for interest payments.

Source: PWC, 'Luxembourg: Corporate Income determination' (PWC, 2 July 2020) <<https://taxsummaries.pwc.com/luxembourg/corporate/income-determination>> last accessed 12 August 2020; PWC, 'Luxembourg: Taxes on Corporate Income' (PWC, 2 July 2020) <<https://taxsummaries.pwc.com/luxembourg/corporate/taxes-on-corporate-income>>last accessed 12 August 2020

Appendix B

Figure 3.
Payments for Intangible Assets.

A multinational group of companies (AB) composed of two companies. Company A located in Australia – a high tax jurisdiction and Company B located in the Netherlands – a favourable tax jurisdiction for payments concerning intangible assets.

Appendix B

Figure 4.

Hybrid Entities and the “Double Irish with a Dutch sandwich”.

Tax avoidance structure between fully owned subsidiaries, involving business transactions in Ireland, Bermuda and the Netherlands.

Source: UNCTAD based on Fuest et al. (2013b); United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, *World Investment Report 2015: Reforming International Investment Governance*, (World Investment Report, 2015)

Appendix C

Table I.
Top 50 US software, hardware and internet firms.

Permanent Establishment (PE)	Number of Companies	Overseas (\$ m)	Overseas (\$ m)	Tax %
		Income	Tax	
Ireland	19	79.730	4.568	5,7%
In major markets	13	22.115	5.538	25%
Switzerland	8	3.724	377	10,1%
Netherlands	5	4.324	239	5,5%
Unclear	4	3.800	942	24,85%
Luxembourg	1	-338	22	-

Notes

- Most of the big tech MNGs have a tax base outside their major markets.
- Source: Company accounts Reuters 2013

Source: Tom Bergin, 'It's not just Google...' [2013] Reuters Special Report 1- 9;

